

Streamlining Serial Communication Protocol Development on SoC Platforms for Code Reusability

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Abstract—In IoT and wearable systems based on System on Chip (SoC), wired communication with off-chip devices is an essential part of the design. Developing this communication interface is not trivial and often application-dependent, which limits the reusability of the code. This paper presents an effective method to simplify the development of communication interfaces and reduce their dependency on specific applications by providing useful design guidelines. In particular, our study targets complex computing platform such as heterogeneous SoCs, which integrate a general purpose processor and a Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) based programmable logic where hardware accelerators can be implemented. As a result of this work, we have developed a software library that can be reused for all devices utilizing i²c serial communication.

Index Terms—Communication protocol, Hardware and Software co-design, SoC, FPGA.

I. INTRODUCTION

In all computing systems, before processing the data, if the data are not already available (e.g. stored in memory), it is necessary to acquire them. To do this, sensors, external to the processing unit, need to acquire real data from the environment in which they are integrated. Independently from the type of sen-

sors (e.g., temperature, motion, etc...), these can be divided into two major families: *digital sensors* and *analog sensors*. The main difference between the two categories is in the nature of their output signal: in the former case, sensors produce a numerical digital signal (i.e. bits) representing the quantized measured physical quantity; in the latter case, sensors produce a continuous quantity (usually voltage) proportional to the measured physical quantity. The magnitude produced by the latter, before being processed by digital systems, must be converted to digital by an analog-to-digital converter (ADC) and then transferred to the main computing unit. Digital sensors, instead, produce a discrete signal ready to be processed and transferred to a digital system. Communication with the main computing unit is mainly through a serial protocol such as Inter-Integrated Circuit (i²c), Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI), Universal Asynchronous Receiver Transmitter (UART), and Universal Serial Bus (USB) used based on the needs of the application and the sensor capabilities to perform data transfer. Microcontrollers, FPGAs and heterogeneous SoCs, integrating both a general purpose processor and an FPGA logic, are typical computing platforms where IoT and wearable systems can be deployed, and each

of them gives to the designer several options to implement these protocols. As an example, they can be implemented entirely in hardware on a FPGA-based programmable logic, as reported in several previous works dealing with interfacing different sensors with the computing platform. In [4], an SPI Single Master Single/Multiple Slave interfaces was described in Verilog language, simulated using Modelsim and finally verified on a development board containing an FPGA device. Similarly, the work [7] presents a Verilog description of a dual master i^2c interface, developed to control a DC motor, for an FPGA-based implementation. The work [11] describes an i^2c master interface, implemented on an AMD-Xilinx Artix-7 FPGA device, aiming at controlling a real-time clock chip. The authors in [12] developed an FPGA i^2c interface to control a light sensor and a UART interface to communicate with a host PC. In [13], an i^2c FPGA-based interface was developed for the communication with a MEMS-type inertial sensor. Notably, the communication interface has been enhanced with a hardware filter to reduce the noise from the sensor. The main features of a hardware communication interface are the possibility to achieve a high speed data transfer, a low power consumption [5] and a custom configuration, particularly useful when the application must meet special specifications imposed by a standard [6].

The other option is implementing the communication interfaces in software, i.e. demanding their control to a software routine running on a microcontroller or a general purpose CPU. Such an approach has the merit to be more design-friendly than the hardware counterpart, since the interface development requires less design time/effort and it can be easily modified if specifications change over time. Obviously, this flexibility is achieved at the cost of lower performances. As an example, the work [9] shows a comparison between the SPI and UART hardware interfaces, implemented on an Altera FPGA device, and their software implementations, running on the ATmega328 microcontroller. Results revealed that the hardware implementations can be up to $4\times$ faster than their software-based counterparts.

Both a hardware and a software implementations are two possible design options when the computing platform is a heterogeneous SoC, integrating both a general purpose processor and an FPGA logic on the

same chip. Such a kind of devices allows the designer to apply a hardware/software co-design approach, by exploiting both the speed capability of a hardware accelerator and the flexibility of a software code. It consists in mapping the timing-critical computational tasks into hardware accelerators hosted in the FPGA logic, and demanding the non timing-critical portions to software routines running on the general purpose processor. Such an approach has the merit to reduce the design effort of the system since the development of the software routines is less timing consuming and more flexible. Indeed, the designer can benefit from using high-level programming languages, such as C++ or Python, and dedicated libraries [8], [10]. Moreover, the hardware/software co-design paradigm allows to reduce the FPGA programmable logic occupancy, thus facilitating the implementation of hardware accelerators also into low-power heterogeneous SoC with a limited amount of hardware resources. As a consequence, demanding the control of the communication interfaces to the general purpose processor is a valuable option to trade the design effort with the system performances. Towards the aim to establish a general framework for the design of an IoT or a wearable computing system on a heterogeneous SoC, a methodology to develop the software routines controlling the communication interfaces between the computational unit and the peripheral sensors would be of great interest.

This paper describes a software library we have designed and implemented that can be exploited and easily reused when a computing platform based on a heterogeneous SoC needs to communicate with sensors and/or peripheral devices via the i^2c protocol. The library has been tested and validated on an AMD-Xilinx Zynq-7000 SoC communicating with a magneto-inertial 9-DOF smart digital sensor via i^2c protocol in normal mode (100kHz).

The paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the implementation of the proposed strategy, the hardware used for testing, and the developed testbed. Section III describes the results obtained and the tests performed to validate the approach. Finally, Section IV concludes the paper.

II. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PROPOSED STRATEGY

In this paper, i^2c communication between a Xilinx's SoC and a magneto-inertial sensor is done, using hardware and software codesign techniques.

The raw data from the sensor is sent via UART serially through COM port and visualized by a serial port monitor software. We conducted our experimental evaluation assuming use of the system in the field of wearable devices where high computation speeds are not needed. For this reason, and given the characteristics of the sensor used, a software-only solution for the communication protocol was chosen so as to optimize resource consumption. The following section describes the characteristics of the adopted development board and the sensor used. Next, the i^2c protocol used to make the two boards communicate is briefly presented. For this purpose it was necessary to properly program the SoC, through the manufacturer's official development environment, AMD Xilinx Vivado. The chip configuration procedure and the developed software are then presented. The latter was designed so that it could be partly reused for other devices that using the i^2c protocol, in order to simplify the development process for future designs.

A. Hardware used and testbed

1) *Development board*: The Cora Z7-07S (Figure 1) is a ready-to-use development board manufactured by Digilent and based on the All-Programmable System-on-Chip (APSoC) Zynq-7000 from Xilinx (AMD).

Fig. 1. Digilent Cora Z7-07S development board.

This board, thanks in part to its low cost, can be used in the consumer environment by demanding hobbyists and makers who require high computing performance. However, unlike a popular and user-friendly platform such as Arduino, which is well documented and supported by a large community, this board and others in the same category are often reserved for more academic and industrial development because of the difficulties in developing applications that require a mix of heterogeneous knowledge in a variety of fields. More in detail,

the development board integrates an XC7Z007S-1CLG400 Xilinx SoC with an FPGA (consisting of 3600 logic cells, 66 DSP slices and 225 KB of Block RAM) and a single core ARM Cortex A9 processor (with a maximum clock frequency of 667MHz). In addition, the board integrate an analog-to-digital converters, many general-purpose input/output pins, a Gigabit Ethernet port, an SD card slot and power solution that allow the Cora Z7 to be used for a vast variety of embedded applications [1].

2) *Sensor*: The BNO055 is a 9-DOF smart digital sensor combining a triaxial 14-bit accelerometer, a triaxial 16-bit gyroscope, a triaxial geomagnetic sensor and a 32-bit cortex M0+ micro-controller running Bosch Sensortec sensor fusion software (BSX3.0 FusionLib), in a single package [2]. The sensor is equipped with digital bi-directional i^2c and UART interface, for configuration and data extraction. More in details the BNO055 can output the following sensor data : [3]:

- **Absolute Orientation** (Euler Vector, 100Hz): Three axis orientation data based on a 360° sphere;
- **Absolute Orientation** (Quaternion, 100Hz): Four point quaternion output;
- **Angular Velocity Vector** (100Hz): Three axis of 'rotation speed' in rad/s;
- **Acceleration Vector** (100Hz): Three axis of acceleration (gravity + linear motion) in m/s^2 ;
- **Magnetic Field Strength Vector** (20Hz): Three axis of magnetic field sensing in micro Tesla (uT);
- **Linear Acceleration Vector** (100Hz): Three axis of linear acceleration data (acceleration minus gravity) in m/s^2 ;
- **Gravity Vector** (100Hz): Three axis of gravitational acceleration (minus any movement) in m/s^2 ;
- **Temperature** (1Hz): Ambient temperature in degrees celsius;

The breakout board (Figure 2), in addition to the sensor, integrates a 3.3V voltage regulator, logic level shifting and pull-up resistors for the reset pin and i^2c communication pins, and a 32.768KHz external crystal for better performance [3].

The i^2c interface of the BNO055 is compatible with the i^2c specification UM10204 and support i^2c clock frequency up to 400kHz [2].

Fig. 2. BNO055 sensor Adafruit breakout board.

3) *Testbed*: Before programming the software, which was necessary to configure the i^2c bus and the sensor, it was necessary to connect the latter to the Cora Z7 development board. Specifically, the SDA and SCL lines of the sensor were connected to the expansion header of the Cora Z7 board, using the pins dedicated to this protocol. The Cora Z7 board requires a voltage of 5V to operate. This power source is provided through the USB connector, which is also used for programming, through the AMD Xilinx Vivado development tool. In this case, the power supplied by the computer's USB port is sufficient to power both the board and the sensor connected to it. In case it is not enough, the board is provided with a separate power connector with a voltage regulation circuit. The BNO055, instead, requires a voltage from a minimum of 2.4V to a maximum of 3.6V this is not a problem, as the development board has a voltage regulator that provides a stable voltage of 3.3V.

B. The i^2c Protocol

The i^2c (Inter Integrated Circuit) protocol is a synchronous, bidirectional, serial protocol developed by Philips Semiconductors (now NXP Semiconductors) in 1982. Only two lines are required for communication (beyond the power lines): *serial data line* (SDA) and *serial clock line* (SCL), connected to a positive voltage source through pull-up resistors. [14]. It allows a communication speed between 100kbit/s to a maximum of 3.4Mbit/s; the speed define the function mode of the protocol. An i^2c bus has two types of nodes: master, which outputs the clock signal, starts and terminates data transmission and slave, which synchronizes on the clock signal. There can be multiple masters and multiple slaves in the bus. Each slave is identified by an unique hardware address; only one master can play this role at the same time. A slave is not permitted to send data unless it has been

specifically addressed by the master [15]. i^2c transaction is initiated by the master sending a START condition and concluded always by the master with a STOP condition. Start and Stop conditions are defined with a specific pattern of the SDA and SCL lines. To communicate with a device connected on the bus, the master sends the slave address followed by a bit identifying whether to perform a write or read operation and listen for a response. If the slave is operational and recognizes its address, it sends an acknowledgment bit (ACK) to master. ACKs also occur on the bus during data transmission after each byte of data correctly received.

In a system, usually the development board is a master and the sensors the slaves. Upon startup, many slave devices need to be configured to establish their behavior. This is usually achieved when the master accesses the slave's internal register maps; registers are specific areas in the slave's memory that hold information. The master needs to write data into these registers to instruct the slave device to carry out a task. Although it is common for i^2c slaves to have registers, not all slave devices include them. Some devices are simpler and have only one register [15].

C. Block Design

Once the hardware connection between the development board and the sensor was made, it was necessary to configure the processor within the SoC, in order to use the dedicated bus for this type of communication. The first operation to be performed, after creating a new block design in the Vivado development environment, is to import the processor and enable one of the two i^2c interfaces (Figure 3) with which the ARM Cortex A9 processor (that integrate the development board together with the FPGA) is equipped, into the I/O planning GUI.

Once this is done, it is necessary to connect the interface to the external pins of the board by clicking on the "Make External" option at the pins on the processor schematic (Figure 4).

The next step is to edit the constraint file (XDC file) describing the board, enabling the pins chosen for communication and setting the same name used in the VHDL wrapper file describing the hardware designed in the block design window. The final steps are to synthesize, implement the design and then generate the bitstream. At this point, it is possible

Fig. 3. ZYNQ Processing System configuration tool - Enable serial interface

Fig. 4. Block Design - Pins dedicated to i^2c protocol

to load it on the SoC and continue with the software programming of the processor.

D. Software

All code was developed in the C++ language, taking advantage of the properties of object-oriented programming. In order to obtain reusable code, this has been divided into three levels as described in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Level division of the software for communication.

These three levels from lowest to highest are: iicps, I2C_utility and BNO055. The first two levels can be reused for any application that needs the i^2c protocol. The last level, on the other hand, depends on the specific device that you want to make communicate via the protocol.

The first level is the library made available by Xilinx iicps, which includes all the APIs needed to use the Zynq-7000 or Zynq-UltraScale's built-in IIC controllers.

The second layer consists of a library written specifically and reusable for any project using the i^2c protocol. It integrates within it a number of useful methods that, by exploiting the methods in the iicps library, mask from the developer some technical details. In this way, application developers can focus on the application logic without dealing with the implementation of the communication interface. In particular, the main methods present in this library are the following:

- **Begin(void)**: takes care of initializing the processor's i^2c controller and configuring it according to the specific requirements, based on the parameters defined by the constructor method (i^2c address, communication clock frequency).
- **Read (u8 *MsgPtr, s32 ByteCount)**: performs a read for a number of bytes specified by the *ByteCount* parameter. To perform the read, the signals carried by the SDA and SCL lines must be modified; this is done by the lower level iicps library.
- **Write (u8 *MsgPtr, s32 ByteCount)**: performs a write for a number of bytes specified by the *ByteCount* parameter. To perform the write, the signals carried by the SDA and SCL lines must be modified; this is done by the lower level iicps library.
- **Write_then_read(u8 *write_buffer, size_t write_len, u8 *read_buffer, size_t read_len)**: Performs two successive operation without interrupting communication: write and then read. This method is the most useful and widely used because it is employed by the upper-level library whenever a sensor value needs to be obtained. When one wants to read the value of a specific register of an i^2c slave device, the address of the register to be read is first sent, and then the contents of that register are read. Below is the code for the method that performs what is described:

```
int I2CDevice::write_then_read(u8
↳ *write_buffer, size_t
↳ write_len, u8 *read_buffer,
↳ size_t read_len) {
//xil_printf("Running
↳ write_then_read
↳ Operation\r\n");
```

```

if(write(write_buffer, write_len)
↪  != XST_SUCCESS) {
    xil_printf("write_then_read
↪  Failed\r\n");
    return XST_FAILURE;
}
return read(read_buffer, read_len);

```

The third and final level is not reusable and depends on the specific device that one wants to communicate via the i^2c protocol. The header file of the library tabulates all the register addresses of the BNO055 sensor. The methods in this library take advantage of this information and the methods offered by the lower level library to initialize, configure, and acquire data from the sensor. In particular, the main methods present in this library are the following:

- **begin(operating_mode)**: initialize the sensor: check if the sensor are connected, set the operation mode, set the power mode, and set an external clock source, based on the timing and the information specified in the sensor's datasheet.
- **read8(Reg_addr)**: Read 8 bit from the register with address *Reg_addr* of an i^2c slave device. This method use the `write_then_read()` function of the second level library `I2C_utility`, with the parameter *read_len* constant and equal to one;
- **readLen(Reg_addr, data_readed, data_len)**: Reads the specified number of bytes (*data_len*) from the base register with address *Reg_addr* and save the readed data into *data_readed* variable. This method use the `write_then_read()` function of the second level library `I2C_utility`, with the parameter *read_len* specified by the parameter *data_len*;
- **Write8(Reg_addr, data_to_write)**: Write 8 bit into the register with address *Reg_addr* of an i^2c slave device;
- **bno055_read_<sensor_name>(data_readed)**: reads the raw value of the sensor from the corresponding register. <sensor_name> can be `acc_x`, `gyr_x`, ... Remember that the sensor acquire data with a 9 DOF, so three value from each sensor (accelerometer, gyroscope and magnetometer) can be acquired. Each sensor for each DOF store the data into two register of 8bit, so to obtain the final value, the registers containing the most significant bits and the least significant bits are first read sequentially, then the most significant bits are shifted to the

left by 8 bits.

Other methods in the library allow obtaining the values already pre-processed by the data fusion algorithm, as well as characteristic sensor information, such as the calibration values of the three sensors or system status information.

III. RESULTS AND VALIDATION

To characterize the proposed system, tests were conducted on the time taken by the software to acquire raw data from the various sensors and tests on the power dissipated by the boards during operation. For the timing test, the global timer in the Arm Cortex-A9 MPCore was used to measure the time before and after the code executed the reading from the sensor, utilizing the previously described library stack. With a frequency of the MPCore of 650MHz and a serial clock frequency of 100kHz (i^2c normal mode), to acquire the raw value of a sensor (accelerometer, gyroscope, or magnetometer) relative to one degree of freedom, the software takes on average 1.73ms. During this period of time, the master initiates communication by sending the start bit and the address of the slave device with the bit signaling a subsequent write. Next, when the master receive the ACK bit from the slave, it sends the address of the register where to go to read the information (in this case the address that contains the least significant 8 bits of the 16-bit value). After receipt of the ACK from the slave, the master again initiates a transaction by sending the start bit and the slave address with corresponding read bit. The master then receives an ACK bit from the slave followed by the 8 bits of the register pointed by the address sent earlier. The master then sends an ACK and when the slave receives it, it sends another 8 bits from the register that contains the most significant 8 bits of the 16-bit value. The master ends the conversation by sending an ACK bit followed by a NACK bit, followed again by a STOP bit. In total, to acquire raw data (not processed by the data fusion algorithm) from the accelerometer, gyroscope or magnetometer the transaction consists of 49 bits. For the power consumption test, we used the Power Profiler Kit II from Nordic Semiconductor, a low-cost instrument for measuring power consumption in embedded applications. It can measure currents from a few nanoamperes up to 1 A, with a resolution ranging of 100nA. For the measure it was used in

Ampere Meter mode: an external power supply provides voltage levels to the device under test (DUT). In this case, the DUT is the Cora Board connected with the BNO055 breakout sensor. The development board, which supplies voltage to the sensor, can be powered via USB cable or via external power supply. To program the board and measure the current draw, a USB cable was modified by interrupting the power supply line. This is then connected in series with the amperometric inputs of the PPKII. Figure 6 shows the setup for power measurement. The measurement was performed while running software that acquired data from the accelerometer with a sampling frequency of 100Hz.

Fig. 6. Power analysis setup

From the value obtained, it can be seen that this methodology does not constitute a major bottleneck in terms of timing for the system and therefore can be handled sequentially by the processor even in more complex applications, where the MPCore also performs other functions besides managing the i^2c interface. About the dissipated power, the value measured is 274.16mA considering that all other peripherals on the development board are also powered, even if they are not used for the purpose of this work.

To further validate the development process based on this methodology, we tried to implement another slave device, reusing the two library layers analyzed in the dedicated section. In particular, we chose to use an 128x64 Dot Matrix OLED display controlled by the popular SSD1306 driver that integrate contrast control, display RAM and oscillator. The controller and the display were placed on a breakout board from Adafruit [17] that integrate even a voltage regulator and built-in boost converter for use the display with a voltage from 3V to 5V indifferently. Data/Commands are sent from MCU through SPI or i^2c interface [16].

The third level library, which is highly dependent on the slave device to be controlled, was rewritten based on information in the controller’s datasheet.

Although the two devices used as slaves are completely different in nature, much of the work was facilitated by the reuse of the two lower level libraries; in fact, the development time was more than halved.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, an approach to implement in a Soc a serial communication protocol has been proposed by exploiting hardware and software co-design techniques, in order to optimize resource consumption. Through this approach it is also possible to make the code reusable for a variety of applications thus facilitating the development process. Finally, this method can be easily adopted by developers who are unfamiliar with hardware development, in languages such as VHDL or Verilog. Testing with the board and sensor has shown that this method works and is applicable. Once the data have been acquired, they must be processed. In the light of edge computing, processing should take place as close as possible to where the data are produced. SoC devices are the ideal platform to meet this requirement, as they have the programmable logic section that can be used to perform in an optimized way even complicated machine learning algorithms that are not implementable on ordinary microcontrollers. In addition to the ongoing development of the hardware accelerator for real-time user activity recognition, we plan to develop additional libraries for other sensors. These libraries will follow the same methodology to facilitate development on these types of systems, even for non-experts. This approach is similar to what has been done with the Arduino platform, which provides user-friendly libraries that enable easy integration and development for a wide range of sensors and actuators. By doing so, we aim to make these systems more accessible and encourage wider adoption in various applications.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We acknowledge co-funding from Next Generation EU, in the context of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan, through the Italian MUR, PRIN 2022 Project “COCOWEARS” (A framework for Continuum Computing WEARable Systems), n. 2022T2XNJE (CUP: H53D23003640006, CUP: H53D2300365000)

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